

A Leave-One-Out Approach to Evaluating Producers' Commodity Dependent Impact Scores on a Non-Calibrated Survey

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel application of the leave-one-out (LOO) methodology to evaluate the impact of individual records on national agricultural estimates produced based on non-calibrated surveys. Using the July 2020 Cattle Survey as a case study in our analysis, it is demonstrated how impact scores generated through the LOO approach can be employed in conjunction with response propensity scores to reduce sample size without significantly affecting the accuracy of estimates. Our findings indicate that strategic sample reductions can enhance resource efficiency in large-scale agricultural surveys and mitigate bias introduced by non-response through targeted imputation. This study contributes to the broader discussion on improving the cost-effectiveness of agricultural data collection while preserving statistical rigor.

Keywords: Impact Scores, Agriculture, Leave-one-out

1. Introduction

The United States Department of Agriculture's (USDA) National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) plays a critical role in the collection, analysis, and dissemination of agricultural data, which informs decision-making for policymakers, industry stakeholders, researchers, and more. These data, collected through extensive surveys and the U.S. Census of Agriculture, serve as the foundation for producing national estimates that influence agricultural policy and market decisions (USDA NASS, 2024). However, fiscal constraints often necessitate reductions in survey sample sizes, potentially compromising the precision and reliability of the resulting estimates.

The challenge posed by sample size reductions is particularly evident in the context of large-scale agricultural surveys, where the balance between data quality and resource constraints is a constant consideration. To address this challenge, we explore the application of the leave-one-out (LOO) methodology to survey data. LOO is a statistical

approach that evaluates the influence of individual records on the overall estimate by systematically excluding each record and recalculating the estimate (Cochran, 1977; Lohr, 1999). This technique, when combined with propensity scores—which quantify the likelihood of responding based on historical data—can serve as a powerful tool for optimizing survey samples with multiple categorical variables without introducing significant bias or error (Rao & Scott, 1984).

This paper focuses on the July 2020 Cattle Survey as a case study to demonstrate the practical application of the LOO combined with propensity scores approach. The USDA NASS Cattle Survey employs a survey design aimed at capturing data on the cattle population, inventory changes, and production patterns across the United States. The sample design uses a stratified approach. Stratification is based on variables such as state, cattle operation type (e.g., beef or dairy), and size, allowing for nuanced data collection that reflects the structure and distribution of cattle operations. The survey includes a mix of probability-based sampling, wherein operations are selected with known probabilities, within strata, which ensures coverage of major cattle-producing areas. The use of stratification reduces sampling variance and allows for more accurate estimates across different segments of the industry.

The survey is conducted through a multi-modal data collection process, combining telephone interviews, online reporting, and mailed questionnaires to maximize response rates and reduce non-sampling errors. The design includes mechanisms to adjust for non-responses and underreporting (lack of coverage) through statistical weighting, ensuring that the estimates remain unbiased and representative of the target population. Data collection typically occurs biannually, allowing NASS to track seasonal and annual changes in cattle inventories and market dynamics. The Cattle Survey provides critical, high-quality data for agricultural economists, policymakers, and industry stakeholders, supporting informed decision-making and economic analysis in the U.S. cattle sector.

Section 2 describes the strategy used to identify the candidates for removal or imputation. Findings from an application of the LOO combined with propensity scores approach to (publicly available) 2020 Cattle Survey data are presented in Section 3, and final remarks are presented in Section 4.

2. Methods

The leave-one-out (LOO) approach is an established technique used to assess the contribution of individual observations to an overall estimate by iteratively excluding each record from the dataset and recalculating the estimate (Arlot & Celisse 2010). In this

study, the LOO strategy was employed to evaluate the impact of individual records from the 2020 Cattle Survey on the commodity of total cattle. The absolute difference between the original total cattle and the recalculated total cattle provides an impact score (IS) for each record i (Cochran, 1977; Deville & Särndal, 1992),

$$IS_i = |Y_{total} - Y_{total_i}|,$$

where Y_{total} is the original national estimate with all records, Y_{total_i} is the national estimate with record i excluded.

The impact score serves as a relative measure of the influence of each individual record on the overall survey estimate, allowing for comparisons across different operations. A higher impact score indicates that the exclusion of a specific record would cause a greater change in the national estimate, thus suggesting that this record has a more significant impact on the survey results. Conversely, smaller impact scores signify that the record's absence would lead to minimal changes, indicating lower importance to the final estimates. It is important to note that these scores are relative to one another; therefore, if one operation has a higher impact score than another, it implies that the former is more influential on the survey's estimate. Understanding these scores is critical, as it helps prioritize which records are essential to retain for maintaining the accuracy of estimates and which ones could be considered for removal or imputation with minimal effect.

In addition, incorporating propensity scores was a critical component of the analysis. A record's propensity score is defined as the estimated probability that the responder associated with that record will respond to the survey. In our case study, a five-year survey response average (\bar{x}) was used as the propensity score for each record, which helped mitigate biases (Groves & Couper, 1998). Let x_i be the response variable for year i where $x_i = 1$ is a valid response to the survey and $x_i = 0$ is a non-response to the survey.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{5} \sum_i^5 x_i$$

Standardized impact scores (m) were then graphed against standardized propensity scores (p), and the distance ($distance = m^2 + p^2$) of each record from the origin of the graph was calculated. This distance represented the refined impact score (hereafter referred to as the propensity and impact score or "pi score"), integrating both impact and propensity preliminary pi scores and propensity scores were normalized. Records with both negative preliminary pi scores and propensity scores were identified and placed into a separate list as candidates for removal or imputation. These candidates were then sorted from greatest to least based on their pi scores, with the top record indicating the most impactful and least likely to respond. Selection for removal or imputation followed a top-

down approach.

3. Results

The study investigated the effects of sample reduction or imputation at the 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% levels. In the scenario of sample reduction, bias to the total cattle estimate was significant. The USDA NASS uses strata as part of their survey sample methodology to group segments of the population with similar characteristics together to improve efficiency and accuracy of estimates. Generally, lower pi scores were associated with records from smaller operations in lower strata, indicating their exclusion would minimally affect the overall estimates. However, the exclusion of these smaller records resulted in a disproportionate removal of records in lower strata (Figure 1), which resulted in inflated variance estimates of those strata. The inflated variance estimates from the lower strata caused an upward bias in the national cattle estimates from 2% to nearly 5% at the 20% removal level (Figure 2.), highlighting the importance of imputing the flagged records rather than removing them.

Imputation of flagged records prior to data collection, particularly from smaller operations, was found to preserve the integrity of the overall estimates with a small downward bias(Figure 3). Figure 3 illustrates how bias was restricted to less than 2% across all levels of imputation. These empirical findings highlight reducing survey cost through imputation as a viable alternative to discontinuing a survey.

Figure 1: Distribution of pi scores across strata.

Figure 2: Effect of sample reduction on national estimates.

Figure 3: Comparison of Estimated Cattle Numbers after sample reduction via imputation

4. Discussion

The leave-one-out approach combined with propensity scores offer a tool for optimizing agricultural survey data collection. This tool allows for targeted sample reductions without compromising data accuracy. By identifying records with minimal impact on national estimates, this approach facilitates the strategic imputation of records, particularly those from smaller operations with lower response rates.

One of the key findings of this study is the potential for sample reductions of up to 20% in the 2020 Cattle Survey data without significant loss of accuracy in estimation (less than 5%) when imputation is employed to account for missing or low-impact data points. This finding is particularly relevant in the context of budgetary constraints faced by NASS and similar organizations.

Despite its advantages, the leave-one-out method has its limitations, including the assumption that historical data can accurately predict future behaviors of responders. Additionally, the computational demands of recalculating estimates for large datasets may pose challenges for organizations with limited processing capacity. Future research should explore the scalability of this method across different commodities and survey contexts.

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